

Stability Constants of 7- α (Anilino Benzyl) 8-Quinolinol Ligand with Cu,²⁺ Ni,²⁺ Zn,²⁺ VO²⁺ Metal Ions

K. J. SHAH, Y. N. BHATT, K. K. PATEL and R. S. PATEL*

University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

Manuscript received 5 January 1976; revised 10 May 1976; accepted 7 June 1976

The proton ligand stability constant of 7- α (anilino benzyl) 8-quinolinol and the stepwise stability constants of its complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), VO(II) have been determined in dioxane : water (70 : 30 v/v) system by potentiometric method at 25 $\pm$ 1 $^\circ$. The stability constants have been determined by several computational methods such as Half integral, Olerup, Least square and Linear plots methods. The order of stability is VO(II) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II).

LIGANDS such as 7- α (substituted) 8-quinolinol are studied to a limited extent pH metrically. Here 7- α (Anilino benzyl) 8-quinolinol (ABQ) is studied with metals like Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and VO(II). The formation constants for these metals were calculated by Calvin and Wilson pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants are determined in 70% v/v dioxane : water medium.

Experimental

The ligand 7-(α -anilino benzyl) 8-quinolinol was synthesized and crystallised¹ to get analytically pure. The solution of ABQ was prepared in dioxane (BDH, AnalaR) which was further purified by standard method². Metal nitrates used were of AnalaR grade which were estimated by standard volumetric and gravimetric methods. A Philips pH meter was used for pH measurements. pH meter was calibrated with buffer solutions having pH 4.3 and 9.1 at 25 $\pm$ 1 $^\circ$.

All titrations were carried out in a 100 ml beaker kept in water thermostat maintained at 25 $\pm$ 1 $^\circ$. Each titration was repeated to get reproducible results. The metal ligand ratio was maintained 1 : 5.

Blank titrations : A mixture of 2.0 ml of 0.1M HNO₃, 5.0 ml of 1M KNO₃, 35 ml of dioxane and 8.0 ml of water (to make the total of 50 ml in all titrations) was titrated with 0.2M NaOH until the pH rose to about 12.

Ligand titrations : A mixture of 2.0 ml of HNO₃, 5.0 ml of 1M KNO₃, 5.0 ml of 0.01M ligand solution in dioxane, 30 ml of dioxane and 8.0 ml of water was titrated with 0.2M NaOH solution.

Metal titrations : A mixture of 2.0 ml of HNO₃, 5.0 ml of 1M KNO₃, 5.0 ml of 0.01M ligand, 1.0 ml of 0.01M metal nitrate solution (for Vanadium VOSO₄ solution), 30 ml of dioxane and 7.0 ml of water was titrated with 0.2M of NaOH solution.

Results and Discussion

The practical proton-ligand stability constants for the ligand was calculated with the help of $\bar{n}_A$ values at different B values (pH meter readings in 70% v/v dioxane : water medium). $\bar{n}_A$ is calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti³ as adopted by Jabalpurwala *et al.*⁴. Plot of log $\bar{n}_A$ against B is done to obtain a best straight line. For this straight line, the values of the practical proton ligand stability constant was obtained by using the relation :

$$\log {}^pK_1^H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A}$$

The proton-ligand stability constant obtained is 12.27 for metal ligand stability constants. $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated by the method of Jabalpurwala *et al.*⁴. The values of $\bar{n}$ are plotted against pL. The values of log K_1 and log K_2 were calculated by half-integral method. The values for log K_1 and log K_2 are approximately same. So they are also computed by least square method⁵, linear plots method⁶ and by Olerup's method⁷.

The average stability constants obtained by different methods are given in Table I. It is observed that the stability constants are in the order

To check the validity of the results $\bar{n}$ was re-calculated using K_1 and K_2 of least square method. The values of standard deviation were calculated. The values are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Metal	log K_1	log K_2	log β_2	σ
H ⁺	12.27	—	—	—
Cu ²⁺	11.80	10.80	22.60	0.08
Zn ²⁺	10.05	9.50	11.55	0.12
VO ²⁺	11.97	11.01	22.98	0.10
Ni ²⁺	10.80	10.17	20.96	0.075

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. K. A. Thaker, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar, for providing laboratory facilities, to C.S.I.R., New Delhi and Gujarat State for the award of scholarship to Y.N.B. and K.K.P. respectively.

References

1. J. P. PHILLIPS, R. KEOWN and Q. FERNANDO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **74**, 4306.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text-book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, 1961, p. 177.
3. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
4. K. E. JABALPURWALA, K. E. VENKATCHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **266**, (a) 1927, (b) 1011.
5. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
6. F. E. CONDON, "Study Projects in Physical Chemistry", Academic Press, 1963, p. 77.
7. H. OLEBUP, *J. ARNAKLORIDERNAS KOMPLEXITATE (diss.)*, Lindstendts Universities, Bokhandel, Lund, 1944.